

europaean **energy**innovation

Connecting Europe's Stakeholders in Energy and Transport

PROTECTING CONSUMERS

ENERGY POVERTY

BUILDING DECARBONISATION

WASTE INCINERATION

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FOREST

Funded by
the European Union

Advanced lightweight materials for energy-efficient structures

Insight

The FOREST project will develop innovative bio-based polymers & additives and recycled carbon fibres that will facilitate the decarbonisation of the transport sector for the next three and half years. The project will contribute to the decarbonisation of the transport sector by developing and implementing innovative bio-based polymers & additives and recycled carbon fibres.

Concept

FOREST will develop novel lightweight multifunctional biocomposites as a competitive alternative to conventional composites.

New chemistries will be developed based on bio-based materials

(reactive and nonreactive polymeric system and fire-retardant additive) in combination with fully recycled carbon fibre and EMI particles.

These biocomposite candidates will be obtained using one-shot manufacturing techniques, involving Out-of-Autoclave (OoA) processes to build and test prototypes (TRL5) with improved multifunctional properties (mechanical resistance, fire-retardant, EMI-shielding) for transport application.

FOREST will increase the focus area on the sustainability in Circular

Economy (CE) by effective circularity solutions applied to multifunctional biocomposites constituents with >50% sustainable materials contain in the lightweight products.

Goals

FOREST project will contribute to the decarbonisation of the transport sector by developing and implementing innovative bio-based polymers & additives and recycled carbon fibres. The goal will be achieved by combining three key drivers: **Reduce, Recovery, and Reshape.**

forest-project.eu

PATHWAY TO MOBILITY DECARBONIZATION

About FOREST Project

FOREST is a 42-month research project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101091790 with €4.3 million in funding. The research consortium is made of 14 partners from 8 different countries. The project is coordinated by AIMPLAS - Plastics Technology Centre set in Valencia, Spain.

Start date: December 2022

Duration: 42 Months

Project coordinator: AIMPLAS – ASOCIACION DE INVESTIGACION DE MATERIALES PLASTICOS Y CONEXAS

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